

Pea Protein

like-a-pro.eu

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LIKE-A-PRO is a EU-funded project aiming to facilitate sustainable and healthy diets by mainstreaming alternative proteins and products, making them more available, accessible and acceptable.

Pea Protein Benefits

Pea is a nutritionally dense legume valued for its high protein content (20-25%) and abundance of vitamins, minerals, dietary fibre, and bioactive compounds.

Pea protein is also hypoallergenic, positioning it as an attractive alternative to soy or dairy proteins and contain several bioactive functions such as antioxidant, antihypertensive, anti-inflammatory, cholesterol-lowering and microbiota-modulating effects.

Extraction Challenges

However, protein extraction from legumes is not fully deployed yet as existing extraction processes (e.g., chemical, mechanical, biological extraction) carry technical limitations. Such as protein denaturalisation, low protein purity, low yield or high costs.

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Optimised Extraction Process

As part of LIKE-A-PRO project, **SANYGRAN** optimised and upscaled its extraction process to obtain an innovative protein ingredient derived from *Pisum sativum*, through a fully mechanical, solvent-free and energy-efficient fractionation process that guarantees safety, nutritional quality, and robust functional performance.

The ingredient obtained has the below key features

High functional performance

Protein rich concentrate (~55% protein), highly **versatile ingredient** with **strong emulsification**, **good foaming behaviour**, and **favourable water- and oil-holding capacities**, supporting texture and stability in beverages, bakery, sauces, meat analogues and hybrid foods.

High Nutritional Value with Proven Digestibility

With 55% protein and a **balanced amino acid profile**, pea protein delivers **high nutritional quality**. Its **excellent digestibility**, while **low presence of anti-nutritional factors** supports its use in nutrient-dense, health-promoting foods.

Sustainable, clean-label extraction

Produced through a **mechanical, solvent-free process** with **low energy use**, **reduced environmental impact** and **full traceability**, delivering a **non-GMO, allergen-free ingredient** that supports clean-label product development and circular bioeconomy strategies.

Proven scalability and commercial readiness

The pea protein is produced at industrial throughput (~900–1,260 kg protein/h), confirming **commercial-scale feasibility**.

Overall, the service developed by SANYGRAN within the LIKE-A-PRO project integrates traceability, technical support for food manufacturers and a reliable supply of a high-quality, non-GMO, allergen-free plant protein ingredient, offering a **next-generation plant-based protein** designed for food applications requiring performance, sustainability and clean-label properties.

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